

RECOGNIZING THE TRANSFORMATION IN TEACHING AND LEARNING PARADIGMS

**Mr. Sharique Momin And **Mr. Rahul Shah*

**Assistant Professor, Swayam Siddhi college of Management & Research & Degree Night College, Bhiwandi*

***Assistant Professor, Swayam Siddhi college of Management & Research & Degree Night College, Bhiwandi*

Abstract :

From ancient to modern times, teaching and learning takes occur directly or indirectly in many forms (formal, non-formal, and informal) at various levels (primary, secondary, and higher education). Here, the manner of teaching and learning has been altering, deliberately or unknowingly, in response to societal change. Teaching and learning in the current day takes place in a well-designed school environment, which is the principal source of competent human resources. The need of the hour is to eliminate paradigm shifts in the teaching and learning process in order to improve this major and dominating activity.

Key words: *Teaching, Learning, Paradigm shift*

Copyright © 2022 The Author(s): This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY-NC 4.0) which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium for non-commercial use provided the original author and source are credited.

Introduction :

In this physical and humanistic world, the only constant is change, which occurs in all disciplines, including agriculture, medical, and industrial operations, as well as the teaching and learning process. People have an intrinsic desire to learn new things and adopt new strategies. Human behavior evolves as a result of innovations, and human behavior also leads to new inventions. It does not follow that all inventions and adaptations will result in a healthy society. It is important to remember that healthy new technology must be adopted and that a sustainable humanism must be transmitted. The paradigm shift, adaptability, and flexibility are always vital in the field of education to improve teaching and learning effectiveness.

Teaching and learning have been going on since the beginning of time, and it has always been about passing on information to the next generation. To make the student more comfortable, to enjoy the learning process, and to improve traditional teaching and learning, new technologies and methodologies must be used as a paradigm shift. Globalization, industrialization, population increase, societal changes, and other variables all contribute to thinking about a paradigm shift in teaching and learning.

A Review of Growth of Technology and Learning :

Teaching and learning began with our forefathers and will continue as long as humans exist on the planet. The technology/technique is represented in all sectors such as agriculture, medical, physical science and human science, space science, and it began when an animal began to wear leaves, animal skin, and attempted to conceal their body. Then they began farming and discovered how to make and use fire, as well as inventing the wheel. We still have a lot of advanced technology from this ancient age, and it will continue as long as the world exists. In general, technology/technique makes humans more comfortable in all fields, including education, where it aids in teaching and learning that is superior than prior levels of acquiescence. To grasp this, a better knowledge of the terms "technology in education" and "technology of education" is required.

Technology in Education

Technology in education refers to the use of hardware and software products in the teaching and learning process. Pen, paper, typewriter, television, radio, x-ray machine, teaching machine, computer, cell phone, internet, and so on.

Technology of Education

Education technology refers to the process or method of teaching. Speech, lecture technique, memorization, debate, drill, peer tutoring, project, assignment, mentorship, seminar, workshop, field/industrial trip/visit, and so on are all examples of classic and modern approaches.

Use of Technology in the Classrooms :

Classroom instruction has changed dramatically as a result of technological advancements. There are a variety of technology tools that are used in the classroom. Black and white boards are being phased out in favour of smart boards. Smart boards may be used for writing, power point presentations, and video presentations, among other things. It functions similarly to a computer, allowing all commands to be executed. Projectors have become an essential feature of schools, and they may be used to display various types of educational materials, including those that can be accessible over the internet. Teachers can prepare their teaching materials and disseminate knowledge using PowerPoint presentations. This may be a really useful tool for instructors in terms of recalling things in the classroom. PowerPoint presentations may also be used to give students homework and have them deliver them. This is proven to be a useful tool for pupils to improve their communication abilities. Students acquire confidence and learn how to communicate their material.

Teachers and students both utilise computers, laptops, and tablets in the classroom. Students can utilise computers for simultaneous comprehension and hands-on experience, or the instructor can use one computer or laptop for instructing. The audio-visual medium allows for a better knowledge of the subject and a higher retention rate. The use of the internet in the classroom aids in the delivery of lessons through simulation activities. Through simulation, students may trade and invest in the stock market. They can also operate in virtual organisations and assume management responsibilities. Virtual reality programmes give students hands-on learning opportunities. Virtual reality

programmes give students hands-on learning opportunities. Classroom education has become more engaging and understandable because to technological advancements.

Government institutions, such as Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalaya, have recognised the importance of technology. They've implemented digital learning in all 500 of their schools' classrooms. They teamed up with Samsung to give digital education to more than 2.5 lakh pupils and 8000 instructors. The majority of Jawahar Navodaya Vidyalaya schools are in rural regions. Teachers have observed lower absence and dropout rates since implementing digital learning. Through the use of technology, students learn to be participatory. According to EdTech Review there has been increased use of online tools in 2015. It has increased from 47% to 53%. 48% of teachers who reported an increase are in the age group of 45-60 years. 14% use online tools inside the classrooms every day and 31% use it almost every day. Top 5 most used tech tools in the classrooms are Micro soft power point, Microsoft word, google chrome, google apps and google classrooms.

Distance and Online Learning :

Learning is expanding beyond the classroom and blurring the lines between disciplines. Virtual or online learning is becoming increasingly popular. For students studying a variety of courses, distance education is becoming increasingly popular. Students who live in rural and isolated places where getting an education is difficult have the option of continuing their studies. Working professionals have the advantage of furthering their education while working. Several people are forced to work owing to family obligations, and these people can benefit from distant education. It also leads to greater qualifications, which may assist working executives advance in their careers. There are various online short-term certification courses available for students and working professionals who want to improve their abilities. Several universities and institutes, including as Patna University, Amity University, IIMs, XLRI, IMT Ghaziabad, Symbiosis, and others, have introduced remote learning to their normal educational offerings. According to the AISHE Report, distant education is becoming more popular at the undergraduate, graduate, and certification levels. This tendency may be seen in the data on student enrolment percentages in 2015-16.

Government of India has brought about major reforms in education sector for bringing about improvement in quality and access to education. Government's initiative includes the following

1. SWAYAM MOOC site (Study of Webs of Active Learning for Young Aspiring Minds)- It is an indigenous MOOC portal that offers free high-quality education to everyone, at any time and from any location. It contains courses taught by some of the greatest professors in the country, as well as e-reading materials, video lectures, a discussion forum, and an evaluation system that awards credits to successful students.
2. The National Digital Library (NDL) is a virtual library of learning resources that offers a single-window search. It has already gathered 15 million books and periodicals, and 31 lakh students are taking advantage of the service.
3. Unnat Bharat Abhiyan (UBA)- This effort aims to bridge the technological divide in rural India. 750 higher education institutions are being selected. This initiative is being utilised to adapt existing technologies to meet the demands of the local community.

4. Smart India Hackathon - The goal of this event is to encourage students to think outside the box when it comes to solving societal problems. In 2018, the scope was increased to include hardware as well.
5. Technical Education Quality Improvement Programmes Phase III (TEQUIP-III)- This initiative focuses on the central tribal belt and the northwestern area. A total of Rs. 2600 crore has been spent on increasing the quality of engineering education and research.
6. Operational Digital Board - The government department plans to support the digital board programme at the national, state, and community levels in order to provide community education through the effective use of technology and telecom services, and to convert classrooms in grades IX and up into digital classrooms.
7. NCERT (National Council of Educational Research and Training) created E-pathshala to showcase and disseminate all educational e-resources like as audio, video, journals, and a range of other print and non-print materials. On the online and mobile app, 3062 audios and videos, 650 e-books, and 504 flip books have been made accessible so far.

All of these programmes demonstrate that the government understands the value of technology in education. It recognises the far-reaching implications of technology for learning and knowledge advancement. As a result, it has launched a number of projects and programmes in India to digitalize education.

Understanding the Healthy Paradigm Shift in Teaching and Learning :

Humans can grow more comfortable thanks to technology or technique. It is important to recognize that using technology alone will not result in a positive paradigm change in the teaching and learning process. To reclaim, rebuild, and revitalize skills, ethical, social, cultural values, morality, patriotism, and empathy, it is imperative that technology be used in conjunction with conventional educational technologies. It does not imply that all conventional ways must be abandoned; rather, useful ancient methods must be practiced in modern classrooms in order to ensure humanity's survival.

Conclusion :

This research demonstrates how integrating technology into education has resulted in good changes. There are a number of innovative educational technologies that help with both teaching and learning. Digital learning technologies such as PCs, laptops, smartphones, iPads, and smartboards have digitised classrooms. The connection and collaboration between instructors, researchers, and teachers and students has risen. In the learning process, educational technology serve as a backbone of assistance. It increases the reach and accessibility of education for both instructors and pupils. It has increased the number of courses available and made studying more engaging. More students are able to profit from education as a result of technological advancements, since they may learn through online courses and distance education. The usage of technology has improved the efficiency of educational institutions. There are a variety of applications and software programmes that can help with learning and administration. The internet has evolved into a fantastic source of information. Educators, researchers, and students make use of its extensive resources.

The Indian government has recognised the value of technology in education and has implemented a number of changes to incorporate technology into education and learning assistance. e-Yantra, Virtual Labs, National Digital Library, E-pathshala, and other government programmes, websites, and applications provide assistance. The government is also encouraging educational institutions to adopt technology. The eLearning market is booming, and it's expected to hit \$1.96 billion in 2021. Educators and instructors have evolved into facilitators and helpers of the educational and learning process. There is no disputing that technology has altered the educational and learning process.

References :

1. Dash. B.N. (2004). Theories of education and education in the emerging Indian society, Dominant Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi.
2. Jagannath Mohanty, (2007). Modern trends in educational technology, Neelkamal Publications, New Delhi.
3. Mc Gettrick. J (2004). Value Development in Higher Education, Neelkamal Publications, New Delhi
4. Publications, New Delhi.
5. Srinivasan. R. (2006). Innovation in education and educational technology, Ram publishers, Chennai.
6. <http://educationtech.ca>
7. <http://education.unesco.org>
8. www.oxfordabstracts.htm
9. <https://www.useoftechnology.com> › Tec education
10. <https://fedena.com/blog/2015/.../the-role-of-information-technology-in-education.htm...>
11. <https://www.lcibs.co.uk/the-role-of-social-media-in-e>
12. <https://yourstory.com/2018/03/digital-technology-government-schools-rural-india>
13. <https://www.octalsoftware.com/blog/benefits-of-mobile-learning-app-for-kids>

Cite This Article:

**Mr. Sharique Momin And **Mr. Rahul Shah, (2022). Recognizing the Transformation in Teaching and Learning Paradigms. Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal, XI (II), 66-70*